

PROMOWANIE WYŻSZEJ EDUKACJI: DOŚWIADCZENIE UE***Olga Bogoretska****doktor nauk politycznych,**Wschodnioeuropejski Narodowy Uniwersytet im. Lesi Ukrainki**(Lutsk, Ukraine)**e-mail: bogorodecka@gmail.com**ORCID : 0000-0002-5878-0068*

Streszczenie. Wzrost konkurencyjności państw UE do poziomu innych gospodarek światowych, został uznany jako priorytet od samego początku funkcjonowania UE. Nacisk było położono na rozwój gospodarki opartej o system „wiedzy”, co w swój sposób znacząco wpłynęło na kształtowanie się innowacyjnej gospodarki i społeczeństwa informacyjnego. „Wiedza” stała podstawową kategorią dla większości dziedzin życia społecznego w krajach UE. Liczne wspólne deklaracje, rezolucje państw członkowskich UE w dziedzinie edukacji, wprowadzenie ECMS, uruchomienie systemu edukacji w Bolonii i wdrożenie programów mobilności studentów wpłynęły na kształtowanie europejskiej polityki edukacyjnej.

Początek XXI towarzyszył państwom UE nowymi wyzwaniem w dziedzinie europejskiej polityki edukacyjnej. Nowe sposoby upowszechniania informacji, wzrost roli Internetu, nowe technologie komunikacyjne znacząco wpłynęły na standardy europejskiej polityki edukacyjnej. Przede wszystkim szkolnictwo wyższe stało się elementem złożonej marki kraju. Zaobserwowano również rozwój ośrodków naukowych i edukacyjnych w krajach UE, uruchomienie licznych stypendiów i grantów, mobilność studentów oraz pracowników dydaktycznych. Szczególną uwagę zwrócono na kwestię promocji szkolnictwa wyższego w UE, której głównym celem było zwiększenie liczby studentów zagranicznych. System promocji szkolnictwa wyższego w większości krajów europejskich został ukształtowany dość podobnie.

Artykuł przedstawia analizę promocji szkolnictwa wyższego UE w ramach unijnej polityki edukacyjnej. Ten rodzaj polityki łączy zasady UE, jej prawa w dziedzinie edukacji. Analiza specyfiki wdrażania polityki edukacyjnej UE pozwala nam zrozumieć zasady kształtowania systemu promocji szkolnictwa wyższego. Tym samym w artykule przeanalizowano główne cechy kształtowania polityki edukacyjnej UE. Przeanalizowano genezę i ramy prawne promocji szkolnictwa wyższego w UE. Kluczowe unijne programy promocyjne, inicjatywy i działania są prezentowane w artykule.

Słowa kluczowe: polityka edukacyjna, UE, promocja, szkolnictwo wyższe, programy edukacyjne, Erasmus Mundus.

PROMOTION OF HIGHER EDUCATION: EU EXPERIENCE

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Abstract. Enhancing Europe's competitiveness to the level of other world economies has been identified as a priority since the beginning of the EU. The main emphasis was put on the development of the knowledge economy, which significantly influenced the formation of the innovative economy and the information society. "Knowledge" has become a basic category in most of spheres of social life in EU countries. Numerous joint declarations, resolutions of EU Member States in the field of education, introduction of ECMS, initiation of the Bologna education system and implementation of student's mobility programmes influenced the formation of European educational policy.

With the beginning of XXI EU countries have faced new challenges regards European educational policy. New ways of dissemination of information, growth of the role of the Internet, new communication technologies have influenced huge transformations in the standards of European educational policy. First of all, higher education became an element of complex brand of the country. There was also observed a growth of scientific and educational centers in EU states, launching of numerous scholarships and grants for students and teaching staff mobility. A special attention was paid to the promotion of EU higher education with the main aim to increase the number of foreign students. The system of higher education promotion of the biggest part of European countries has been shaped quite similarly. Current research analyzes the promotion EU higher education in the frameworks of EU educational policy. This kind of policy combines EU principles, laws in the sphere of education. The analysis of the peculiarities of EU educational policy implementation provides us with an understanding of the principles of the higher education promotional system formation. Thereby, main features of EU education policy-making are examined in the article. The origins and legal frameworks of EU higher education promotion are analyzed. Key EU promotional programs, initiatives and activities are presented in current research.

Keywords: educational policy, EU, promotion, higher education, educational programs, Erasmus Mundus.

ПРОМОЦІЯ ВИЩОЇ ОСВІТИ: ДОСВІД ЄС

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Анотація. Підвищення конкурентоспроможності Європи до рівня інших світових економік було визначено пріоритетним з початку функціонування ЄС. Основний акцент був зроблений на розвитку економіки знань, що суттєво вплинуло на формування інноваційної економіки та інформаційного суспільства. „Знання” стало основною категорією у більшості сфер суспільного життя країн ЄС. На формування європейської освітньої політики вплинули численні спільні декларації, резолюції держав-членів ЄС у галузі освіти, запровадження ECMS, започаткування Болонської системи освіти та впровадження програм мобільності студентів та викладачів.

З початком XXI країни ЄС зіткнулися з новими викликами у сфері європейської освітньої політики. Нові форми поширення інформації, зростання ролі Інтернету, нові комунікаційні технології трансформували європейську освітню політику. Перш за все, вища освіта стала елементом комплексного бренду країни. Також спостерігається зростання наукових та освітніх центрів у ЄС, започатковуються численні стипендії та гранти для студентів, промується мобільність викладачів. Особлива увага приділялася промоції вищої освіти ЄС з основною метою збільшення кількості іноземних студентів. Система промоції вищої освіти більшості країн ЄС була сформована приблизно однаково. У статті проаналізовано промоцію вищої освіти ЄС у рамках освітньої політики ЄС. Така політика поєднує принципи, закони ЄС у сфері освіти. Аналіз особливостей реалізації освітньої політики ЄС дає нам розуміння принципів формування промоційної системи вищої освіти. Тим самим у статті розглядаються основні особливості формування освітньої політики ЄС. Проаналізовано витоки та правові рамки промоції вищої освіти ЄС. Основні промоційні програми, ініціативи та заходи ЄС представлені в дослідженні.

Ключові слова: освітня політика, ЄС, промоція, вища освіта, освітні програми, Еразмус Мундус.

Outcomes. “Educational policy” in EU is considered as a “plan that aims to influence the current and future decisions of the EU Member States in the field of education, in particular higher education” (*Thieme and Szkolnictwo Wyższe 2009, 45*). According to Polish scholar E. Żyłkiewicz-Płońska, the foundations of European educational policy in the field of higher education were laid in the 1970s. In fact, since the first meeting of the Ministers of Education within the European Community in Brussels in 1971, it is possible to state about the first steps in cooperation as regards education between Member States. The European Commission began an active work in the field of education, creating in the same year the “Teaching and Education Group” and in 1973 a separate Training Center responsible for research and science (*Żyłkiewicz-Płońska 2017, 97*).

The following steps regards shaping European education policy were concerned the adoption of an action program in the field of education, which became the first legal instrument of this kind. It was The Resolution of the Council and of the Ministers of Education, of 1976 comprising an action programme in the field of education (Council, Education 1976). This document outlined, among others, the equal rights of European Community to access to different levels of education, and promotion of scientific mobility among students and teachers. An important element of the Resolution was a necessity to expand links between higher education institutions of the Member States and promotion of cooperation within educational programs in Europe. However, as noted by E. Żyłkiewicz-Płońska, the Resolution, despite its relevance to the public needs of that period, had not been fully implemented. The active development of educational cooperation between the Member States of the European Community began only in the late 1980s with the emergence of educational and scientific programs (*Żyłkiewicz-Płońska 2017, 97*).

Specifically, in 1987, were launched such programs as COMET (“a world-wide leader in support of education and training for the environmental sciences, delivering scientifically relevant and instructionally progressive products and services (UCAR Community Programs. COMET), Erasmus (a program aimed on promoting the mobility of teachers and students (Erasmus), Eureka (an initiative aimed to support of international cooperation in the field of innovation research and development (EUREKA). In fact, those and many other programs have played a significant role in shaping European education policy. After all, the Member States exchange of experience in the educational process, launching internships for student and teachers, have greatly increased the importance and role of higher education in these countries. There was also noticed a growing interest to “improvement of individual competences and skills of the person” (*Żyłkiewicz-Płońska 2017, 99*).

Since 1988 within Erasmus program there was launched the pilot project “European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System”. It was initiated in order to recognize and validate student learning outcomes in the context of international educational mobility. The project was created for 6 years and spread in most of the European Community countries, but for only a few specialties, including Business Administration, Chemistry, History, etc. (ECTS - European Credit Transfer System).

The political and economic transformations of the late 1980s and early 1990s in most European countries, in particular the signing of the Maastricht Treaty by the members of the European Community in 1992, significantly contributed to the gradual improvement of European educational policy. The problem of education in EU countries became a quite important, as it was mentioned in Art. 126 of the Maastricht Treaty, “The Community shall contribute to the development of quality education by encouraging cooperation between Member States and, if necessary, by supporting and supplementing their action, while fully respecting the responsibility of the Member States for the content of teaching and the organization of education systems and their cultural and linguistic diversity” (*Treaty on European Union 1992, p. 47*).

The creation of the EU was accompanied by the construction of a knowledge-based economy. Actually, it was connected with the formation in Europe of the so-called “knowledge economy”. The essence of this concept is based on the knowledge as a driving force of progress. From the very beginning of the creation of the EU, “knowledge” has been identified as one of the key elements in the development of an innovative economy and the formation of an information society.

An important step in the implementation of the common European educational policy was the signing of the Sorbonne Declaration in 1998 by the ministers of four countries, namely France, Germany, the United Kingdom and Italy. The purpose of the Declaration was to create a common system of coordination within the planned European Higher Education Area, where should be promoted mobility for both students and teaching staff. It also aimed to promote relevant qualifications according to the needs of the labor market (European Higher Education Area).

Significant changes to the approaches of higher education consideration within the framework of European educational policy were occurred at the end of the twentieth century. Namely, on June 19, 1999, the Bologna Declaration (known as the Bologna Convention) was signed by the Ministers of Education of 29 countries of Western and Central Europe. This document envisaged the creation of a European Higher Education Area (EHEA) and the introduction of new approaches to the organization of the learning process in EU countries (Спільна декларація міністрів освіти Європи).

The Declaration stated, inter alia:

- adoption of a common system of comparative educational and qualification levels;
- introduction of two cycles of study: bachelor, master;
- development and dissemination of European higher education standards.

Improvement of the European content of modules, courses at all levels;

- implementation of credit and rating system in accordance with the European Credit Transfer System (ECTS);

- ensuring the quality of preparation and recognition of diplomas;

- ensuring the mobility of students and teachers within the European educational space;

- promoting European cooperation in the field of education quality assurance;

- promoting the attractiveness of the European educational space to other regions of the world;

- issuing a European Diploma Supplement to students (*Журавель, Шинкарик 2011, 62*).

It should be mentioned that Declaration contained provisions for increasing the attractiveness of the European educational space to other regions of the world, which could be achieved through the promotion of European higher education. By signing the Declaration, there was started Bologna Process, aimed, among other things, on raising the level of prestige of European higher education institutions over American ones. Thereby, the provisions of the Bologna Declaration became the basis for the promotion of European higher education, and the Bologna Process itself as a driving force in the promotion of European higher education.

In May 2005, an agreement was reached in Bergen at a meeting of Ministers of European countries responsible for higher education, to establish a system of qualifications for a Pan-European higher education area (*Комюніке Конференції Міністрів країн Європи 2005*). Such a system also included a “promotion of European higher education at the continental and global levels. Placing higher education within research, teaching and innovation has identified it as a key factor in increasing Europe’s competitiveness with other global economies” (*Żyłkiewicz-Płońska 2017, 105*).

Importantly, the European Higher Education Area (EHEA) was formally launched in 2010 as a result of the signing of the Budapest-Vienna Declaration. Thus, the main goal of the Bologna Process was achieved. It became “an unprecedented example of regional,

cross-border cooperation in the field of higher education and made European higher education more visible on the world map” (*Будапештсько-Віденська Декларація 2010*). Huge experience in higher education, constant international consultations, realization of students and teaching mobility programs within the Bologna Process have led to the creation of a powerful EHEA, which included the following elements:

- “European countries with different political, cultural and academic traditions would engage in cooperation to reach a shared objective;
- European students and graduates would be able to move easily from one country to another with full recognition of qualifications and periods of study, and access to the European labor market;
- European Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) would be able to cooperate and exchange students/staff on bases of trust and confidence and also of transparency and quality;
- European governments would fit their national higher education reforms into a broader European context;
- Higher Education (HE) in the European region would increase its international competitiveness, as well as enter into dialogue and improve cooperation with HE in other regions of the world” (*European Higher Education Area*).

It is important that the European Higher Education Area allowed European countries not to unify but to adapt their own higher education systems to the common European model. Intensive cooperation between higher education institutions in European countries was implemented through the implementation of various international educational and scientific programs. Through these programs and initiatives, higher education was actively promoted. It should be noted that in addition to Pan-European programs, most of the EU countries have also developed their own agencies for the promotion of higher education. First of all, are considered few Pan-European programs that have become most prominent and have promoted EU higher education.

The Erasmus Mundus Program initiated by the European Commission in 2004. The main objective of this educational initiative was to improve the quality of European higher education and promote mobility among students, teachers from non-EU countries. Erasmus Mundus was also aimed to “restore Europe to a leading position on the international university scene” (European Commission. Erasmus Mundus). This initiative of the European Commission has been divided into three areas of implementation (Erasmus Mundus Programme):

- Erasmus Mundus joint programmes of outstanding quality at masters and doctoral levels;
- Erasmus Mundus Partnerships between European and Third Country higher education institutions included scholarships and fellowships for mobility;
- Promoting European higher education and Europe as an international center of excellence.

The first area involved the support of joint programs at the master’s and doctoral levels, led by a consortium of higher education institutions from EU countries, and later from all over the world. These programs provided an opportunity to obtain dual diplomas from relevant higher education institutions (*Erasmus Mundus 2009–2013 program guide 2013, 24*). The second area was aimed to promote European higher education, in order to improve students’ career opportunities and also to promote intercultural understanding through active cooperation with third countries. The program included partnerships between European higher education institutions and relevant third

country institutions, exchange and mobility at all levels of higher education, including scholarships (*Erasmus Mundus 2009–2013 program guide 2013*, 48).

The most important, according to current research, is the third area of the Program dedicated to the promotion of European higher education. It should be noted that its main objective was to support international initiatives, research, projects and other activities aimed on enhancing the attractiveness, promotion and accessibility of European higher education. The third area of the Program was formed by the following three elements:

- “the promotion and awareness raising of the European higher education sector as well as the relevant cooperation programmes and funding schemes;
- the dissemination of the programme’s results and examples of good practice;
- the exploitation and mainstreaming of these results at institutional and individual level” (*Erasmus Mundus 2009–2013 program guide 2013*, 75).

In 2014, the Erasmus Mundus program was transformed, along with several other EU educational initiatives, into the Erasmus + program, which is planned to be implemented by 2020. This program aims to support education, youth, sports and internships in EU countries. The Erasmus + also had a specific purpose as following:

- to reduce unemployment, especially among young people;
- to promote adult learning;
- to encourage youth to take part in European democracy;
- to support innovation, cooperation and reform;
- to reduce early school leaving;
- to promote cooperation and mobility with the EU’s partner countries (Erasmus+. European Commission).

It should be mentioned that there is a network of national offices of Erasmus+ programme in most of the countries around world. In particular, the network of national offices of the Erasmus + program and national teams of experts on higher education reform operates in Ukraine. It is implemented by the NGO “Institute for Leadership, Innovation and Development”. This structure supports the implementation of Erasmus + and coordinates the activities of the National Expert Team of Ukraine. The main objective of the National Erasmus + Office in Ukraine “to assist the European Commission, the Education, Audiovisual and Culture Executive Agency, the EU Delegations and the Ukrainian authorities in the implementation of the international higher education dimension of the Erasmus+ programme” (National Office Erasmus+ UA).

Along with the transformational changes of the Erasmus Mundus program, in 2015 was launched a key EU project for the promotion of European higher education – “Study in Europe”. Main aims of the project were:

- “to show students worldwide what studying in Europe offers;
- to help international students to find out about higher education study, research and scholarship opportunities in Europe;
- to connect European higher education organizations with international students and partners” (Study in Europe).

Talking about main tools of the “Study in Europe” project, we should underline:

- effective marketing and branding methods;
- using of the “Study in Europe” logo in conferences, educational initiatives, scientific events, etc.;
- development of powerful promotional campaigns;

- holding of higher education fairs to disseminate relevant information about EU higher education.

Currently, “Study in Europe” project covers higher education in 33 European countries, and is a part of the Erasmus + program.

This period we also observe the creation of a complex brand of EU higher education, among others, due to:

- creation of web portal “Study in Europe”;
- realization of powerful information campaign launched in different countries that included the distribution of various materials (brochures, flyers, posters, DVDs in seven languages), etc. (*Riviezzo, De Nisco, Napolitano 2012, 140*).

Italian researchers in the field of higher education emphasize that “Europe aspires to increase its share of the international student’s market, in which the number of internationally mobile students is predicted to rise to 7.2 million by 2025” (*Riviezzo, De Nisco, Napolitano 2012, 140*). Therefore, promotion projects of European higher education, in particular “Study in Europe”, have become the key one to achieve mentioned above aspirations. It should be mentioned that “Study in Europe” does not duplicate national programs of higher education promotion in EU countries, but merely is a “window” into the European higher education area.

At the present stage, the “Study in Europe” web-portal has significantly improved its content and in fact is one of the main sources of information regards higher education in EU countries. The content analysis of this resource allows us to confirm that provided data contains accessible and well-formed information with a focus on the presenting benefits of studying in EU. Web-portal “Study in Europe” is a guide for foreign students that provides with following information:

- general information about EU and each of the member state;
- a detailed description of the European higher education system;
- a profile of each of the EU countries with a short promotional video and the specificities of studies in this country;
- information on tuition fees and scholarship opportunities;
- accommodation;
- Visa and other legal aspects of the stay in EU countries;
- research opportunities;
- news and events (Supporting education and training in Europe and beyond).

Also the web-portal presents benefits of studying in the EU, promoting best teaching practices and innovative techniques in learning process. All those advantages of studying in EU are aimed to influence foreign students and possible applicants for the studies. Thereby, among main benefits are mentioned following asset:

- studies at leading world universities and research centers;
- EU as a leading region in the world as regards the number of scientific publications;
- an availability of a wide range of scholarships for foreign students, that also covers the costs of stay in EU countries;
- organization of various scientific conferences and meetings;
- opportunities for professional trainings;
- availability of individual studying plans and “scientific freedom” in conducting of projects;
- study in English or other European languages;

an opportunity to travel and learn about different European cultures and traditions (Supporting education and training in Europe and beyond).

It is important that the information provided on web-portal “Study in Europe” is available not only in English but also in each official language of EU Member States. Thereby, the access of the applicants to the necessary information highly increases. There was formed a list of EU Member States with references to national promotion agencies or/and official pages of the ministries of higher education. These online resources provide applicants/students with understanding of the peculiarities and specificity of studying in EU.

Thus, the “Study in Europe” project allows:

- significantly expand the number of international students in EU,
- to provide sufficient information about studies in each of EU countries thanks to high quality promotional techniques;
- creation of competitive brand of EU higher education.

It should be also noted that there is a number of other projects and programs that partly have an influence on the promotion of EU higher education. In particular, “Horizon 2020” – the largest EU research and innovation program with a € 80 billion fund for the period of 2014-2020. The main objective of this initiative is to ensure Europe’s global competitiveness by developing world-class science and removing barriers in the development of innovations. “Horizon 2020” also has significant political support from European leaders and Members of the European Parliament (Horizon 2020. European Commission). Within this program were also launched “Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions” – the grants aimed on the development of international mobility of scientists and promote high-quality research in various fields. Also “Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions” was initiated with the idea to overcome existing barriers between the scientific and business environments (Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions).

EU countries in the framework of educational programs realization and close intergovernmental cooperation, have been promoted their own higher education at different regional levels. An active regional cooperation has become a powerful tool for exchanging experience and best practices between European and foreign partners. For example, we present the promotion of EU higher education in Latin America.

According to the European Commission, in 2015 the cooperation of 28 EU Member States was implemented, among other regions, with 18 Latin American countries (Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Cuba, Ecuador, El Salvador, Guatemala, Honduras, Mexico, Nicaragua, Panama, Paraguay, Peru, Uruguay and Venezuela). As part of this cooperation, a powerful information campaign was launched to promote European higher education in Latin American countries. There were several actions that include promotional activities:

1) during 2007-2013 – EU assigned € 556 million for regional programs in Latin America under the “Development Cooperation Instrument”. The main areas were: social cohesion; water management and climate change; private sector development and higher education.

2) during 2007-2013 – EU support of the development of Latin America higher education through the implementation of ALFA III (Latin American Academic Studies) and Erasmus Mundus - Action 2: Partnerships;

3) during 2014-2020 – EU continued to maintained the implementation of the Erasmus+ program in this region (Promotion of higher education).

Each of mentioned above programs in the field of higher education included of several internal projects that were successfully implemented during 2007-2013. In particular, the ALFA III program was aimed at modernizing of Latin America higher education system as a tool of promoting sustainable development in the region. The EU has earmarked € 75 million for the implementation of this program and, together with Latin American countries, has implemented 51 joint projects in the fields of new technologies and innovations; climate change; socio-economic development; inclusive education, etc. (Promotion of higher education). For the realization of “Erasmus Mundus - Action 2: Partnerships 2” in the region, EU has assigned € 95.6 million, that has allowed 6,650 students and scholars to participate in mobility programs.

For the another programme Erasmus+, EU have assigned in 2014-2020 EU €163 million with three group of actions:

- “credit mobility: student mobility between 3 and 12 months (in both directions) to obtain credits in a host institution, which are then recognized by the home institution”;
- joint master degrees;
- “joint projects based on multilateral partnerships to fund curriculum development and modernization, new diplomas, modern teaching and learning practices, improving university governance and management, and creating better links between higher education and the world of work” (Promotion of higher education).

Conclusions. It should be mentioned that significant qualitative and quantitative changes took place in the system of European education policy since signing the Bologna Declaration. Those changes lied in the field of teaching level improvement, comprehensive involvement of foreign students in different educational programmes and complex promotion of EU higher education all over the world.

The beginning of the XXI century and the growth of globalization processes in the world have encouraged European countries to develop new forms of higher education promotion. The best example of this were mobility programmes for students and teacher. Those programmes helped them to acquire necessary skills and competencies and facilitate personality development. Among the most famous and effective programs of this type, we highlight Erasmus Mundus. An initiative that actually created a basis for the development of a European education brand and expanded the mobility of thousands of students from non-EU states. The third action of this Program was “Promotion of European Higher Education”, which increase attractiveness of European higher education around the world. The current stage of realization of this Program is enriched with such important element as, the promotion of adult education. The complex promotion of EU higher education would not be full with “Study in Europe” project. This initiative not just broaden horizons about benefits of EU higher education, but also serves as an information window into the European Higher Education Area for students from all over the world.

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